

Aesthetic limit states and cultural variation in wooden cladding acceptance

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Background

To optimise the use of renewable materials in construction, it is essential to understand the factors influencing decisions throughout their design and service life. Life Cycle Costing (LCC) supports sustainable development by aiming to minimise long-term costs through informed planning of service life, maintenance, and replacement. Central to this is the engineering concept of limit states - Ultimate Limit States (ULS) for structural safety and Serviceability Limit States (SLS) for functionality. However, in non-loadbearing applications such as cladding, maintenance is often driven by aesthetic deterioration rather than structural concerns. These aesthetic limit states are subjective and influenced by user preferences, personality traits, and cultural background (Viholainen et al. 2021). In practice, undesired aesthetic changes are among the main reasons for cladding replacement in Europe, alongside fungal decay and modernisation (Englund 2013). Premature replacement due to insufficient communication about weathering effects and maintenance needs remains under-addressed. By accounting for variation in user preferences, material selection can be tailored to support a longer service life. This study presents multi-country variation in climate-related perceptions of wood and user preferences for wooden cladding.

Keywords: maintenance, life cycle costing (LCC), service life, user perception.

Experimental

An online survey was conducted by IPSOS in July 2023 across Norway, Sweden, and Germany, targeting adults aged 18 to 89. Approximately 1,000 participants per country were recruited from panels representative of age, gender, and region. The final sample comprised 3,112 individuals. The questions about wood and climate were adapted from Lähtinen et al. (2019).

Results and Discussion

Aesthetic service life is largely user-defined. Viholainen et al. (2021) found that perceptions of wood in construction varied across Europe, with respondents from Finland, Norway, and Sweden forming a distinct group, likely reflecting shared regional traditions in timber use. Table 1 presents aggregated survey results, partly supporting the findings by Viholainen et al. (2021). Norwegian and Swedish respondents more strongly agreed that “using wood mitigates climate change” than German respondents. For the statements “wood is a

renewable material” and “wooden structures are very long-lasting,” Swedish and German respondents gave similarly positive responses, and Norwegians were even more affirmative. More respondents, particularly in Norway, found the ‘climate change’ statement difficult to answer, whereas uncertainty among respondents was low for the other two statements. For the same questions, Finnish respondents (Lähtinen et al. 2019) showed agreement levels similar to Norwegians and Swedes, although a higher proportion (32.3%) found the ‘climate change’ statement difficult to answer. For the other two statements, Finnish agreement was also high (92.5% and 88.2%). Lähtinen et al. (2019) concluded that there are two main consumer groups: those who appreciate the ecological and physio-technological benefits of wood, and those who value its aesthetic and well-being qualities.

Experience with living in and maintaining wooden houses was highest in Norway, followed by Sweden and Germany, likely influencing attitudes toward maintenance and durability. Norwegian respondents reported lower tolerance for decay, greater motivation for cleaning and recoating, and longer replacement intervals for cladding boards. For cleaning and recoating, Swedish and German respondents showed similar patterns, whereas Germans were most inclined to replace boards frequently. Replacement intensity, whether replacing all boards or only damaged ones, was similar across countries. The proportion of respondents with no intention to replace cladding was low overall, but highest in Germany, followed by Sweden and Norway. Norwegian and Swedish respondents preferred coated wooden cladding more than Germans, while acceptance of uncoated cladding was consistent across countries (~20%). Based on survey data, three user types were identified: meticulous, average, and unpressured, with national limit states assigned for each.

Table 1. Aggregated summary statistics (%) from the survey.

Questions	Reply	NO	SE	DE
'Using wood mitigates climate change'	completely/partly agree	65.1	69.7	51.7
	completely/partially disagree	34.9	30.3	48.4
	impossible to answer	19.7	10.6	7.0
'Wood is a renewable material'	completely/partly agree	90.2	84.7	84.6
	completely/partially disagree	9.8	15.3	15.5
	impossible to answer	2.2	3.0	1.4
'Wooden structures are very long-lasting'	completely/partly agree	92.0	83.3	82.8
	completely/partially disagree	8.0	16.7	17.2
	impossible to answer	1.3	4.0	1.5
Experience - living in a wooden house	a lot/quite a lot	88.3	55.0	17.0
Experience - maintaining a wooden house	a lot/quite a lot	64.0	39.6	15.3
Cladding preference (coated/uncoated)	coated wooden cladding	54.2	52.8	41.1
	uncoated cladding	17.6	20.2	18.7
Acceptance of decay damage	totally/quite unacceptable	76.0	66.9	64.1
Maintenance: Cleaning interval	4 years or less	64.2	58.3	56.1
Maintenance: Recoating interval	10 years or less	81.1	65.2	67.8
Maintenance: Replacement interval	20 years or less	32.6	54.2	62.0
Maintenance: Replacement intensity	all cladding boards	28.9	25.6	22.9
	only damaged cladding boards	58.2	51.9	56.8
	not change cladding boards	0.8	4.8	6.5
	impossible to answer	12.2	17.7	13.9

Conclusions

Multi-country differences in experience, maintenance attitudes, and aesthetic preferences suggest that tailored communication and material selection strategies are essential to extend service life and reduce premature replacement.

References

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